

Fragebogen

1 Demographics

How much is 12 + 8?

Please fill in the result below.

Do you identify as ...?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

Female

Male

Other

What is the highest level of schooling you have completed?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

8th grade or less

Some high school

High school graduate

Vocational or technical school

Some college

Associate degree

Bachelor's degree

Graduate work

Which religion do you most identify with?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

Catholic

Protestant

Jewish

Muslim

Atheist

Agnostic

Other

Please indicate your type of residence.

Please choose the appropriate answer below

Rural (countryside or village)

- Small town
- Large city in a neighborhood that is not very multicultural
- Large city in a neighborhood that is very multicultural
- Other

What is your age?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- I prefer not to say
- 19 - 24
- 25 - 31
- 32 - 38
- 39 - 44
- 45 - 49
- 50 - 54
- Older

2 Political Background

Do you consider yourself to be liberal, conservative, or somewhere in between?

Please choose the option on the slider that is most appropriate.

- 1 - Very liberal
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7 - Very conservative

Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as a Republican, a Democrat, an Independent, or something different?

Please choose the appropriate option below.

- Republican
- Democrat
- Independent

Neither

Other

Estimate, on a 10-point scale, your degree of interest in "information about what's going on in politics and public affairs".

Please choose the appropriate option on the slider below.

Not interested at all

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

Very interested (follow daily)

Estimate, on a 10-point scale, your level of attention to "information about what's going on in politics and public affairs".

Please choose the appropriate option on the slider below.

Not attentive at all

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

Very attentive (follow daily)

How often do you have political discussions with people who you would say do not share your own convictions?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

Multiple times a day

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Rarely
- Never

Estimate the number of people you talk to face-to-face on average, over the phone or using any type of internet communication about politics or public affairs during a typical week.

Please fill in the appropriate number below.

Do you agree with the current administration's immigration policies?

Please choose the appropriate option on the slider below.

- Not at all
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Fully support it

3 Ideology (enthält Gruppen Trigger)

How often do you think, reading an article/news on traditional media, that it is slanted in any political direction or actively omitting information to drive the reader's perception of the topic into a certain political direction?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

How often do you think, reading an article/news on social/citizen media, that it is slanted in any political direction or actively omitting information to drive the reader's perception of the topic into a certain political direction?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely

- Never

4.1.1 Overview_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see an overview page of different articles. It will give you an orientation of the political classification of each article. Please read the overview carefully. You will be asked a question about it afterwards.

4.1.2 Overview_page (enthält Annotations Trigger 1)

If you need to read the overview again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/O1>

How many political view-points are displayed in the overview?

After reading the article, please answer the question below.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

4.1.3.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.3.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3

- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.1.4.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.4.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million

- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.1.5.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.5.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3

- 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

4.1.6 Re_occurring_end_questions (enthält Annotations Trigger 2)

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - Very impartial
-

4.1.7.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.7.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3

- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.1.8.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.8.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7

- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.1.9.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.9.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.1.10 Re_occurring_end_questions (enthält Annotations Trigger 3)

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2

- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

4.1.11.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.11.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not

entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.1.12.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.12.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7

- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.1.13.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.1.13.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

4.1.14 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2

- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

4.2.1 Overview_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see an overview page of different articles. It will give you an orientation of the political classification of each article. Please read the overview carefully. You will be asked a question about it afterwards.

4.2.2 Overview_page (enthält Annotations Trigger 1)

If you need to read the overview again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/O2>

How many political view-points are displayed in the overview?

After reading the article, please answer the question below.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

4.2.3.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.3.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 A

Please click on the link below and read the article carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards. The link will open up in a new window, so return to this question once you read the article.

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree

- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.2.4.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.4.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9

- Strongly agree

4.2.5.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.5.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree

- 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

4.2.6 Re_occurring_end_questions (enthält Annotations Trigger 2)

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3

- 4
- Very impartial

4.2.7.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.7.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.2.8.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.8.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4

- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.2.9.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.9.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.

- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.2.10 Re_occurring_end_questions (enthält Annotations Trigger 3)

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

4.2.11.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.11.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money

- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.2.12.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.12.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4

- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.2.13.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.2.13.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8

- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.2.14 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

Not at all impartial

2

3

4

Very impartial

4.3.1 Overview_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see an overview page of different articles. It will give you an orientation of the political classification of each article. Please read the overview carefully. You will be asked a question about it afterwards.

4.3.2 Overview_page (enthält Annotations Trigger 1)

If you need to read the overview again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/O3>

How many political view-points are displayed in the overview?

After reading the article, please answer the question below.

1

2

3

4

4.3.3.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.3.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

5.7 million

200 thousand

more than 50 million

less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election

rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.3.4.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.4.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7

- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.3.5.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.5.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.3.6 Re_occurring_end_questions (enthält Annotations Trigger 2)

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial

- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

4.3.7.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.7.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

Strongly disagree

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

Strongly agree

4.3.8.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.8.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

Strongly disagree

2

3

- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.3.9.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.9.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.

- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.3.10 Re_occurring_end_questions (enthält Annotations Trigger 3)

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

4.3.11.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.11.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money

- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.3.12.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.12.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3

- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.3.13.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

4.3.13.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7

- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

4.3.14 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4

- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

5.1 Leere Seite (enthält Annotations Trigger 1)

Please click forward.

5.2.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.2.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

5.3.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.3.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million

- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

5.4.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.4.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 1 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

5.5 Re_occurring_end_questions (enthält Annotations Trigger 2)

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

5.6.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.6.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

5.7.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.7.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9

Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

Strongly disagree

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

Strongly agree

5.8.1 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.8.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 2 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

Strongly disagree

2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

 Strongly disagree 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 Strongly agree

5.9 Re_occurring_end_questions (enthält Annotations Trigger 3)

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

 Very fair 2 3 4

- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

5.10.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.10.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 A

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/FB3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree

- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

5.11.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.11.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 B

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/EB3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9

- Strongly agree

5.12.1 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

5.12.2 Fragebogen Gruppe 1 Artikel 3 C

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/H3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2

- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

5.13 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4

- Very impartial

6.1.1 Overview_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see an overview page of different articles. It will give you an orientation of the political classification of each article. Please read the overview carefully. You will be asked a question about it afterwards.

6.1.2 Overview_page

Please click on the link for the overview below and read it carefully. The link will open up in a new window, so return to this question afterwards.

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/O1>

How many political view-points are displayed in the overview?

After reading the article, please answer the question below.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

6.1.3 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.1.4 Artikel 1

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4

- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

6.1.5 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme

- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

6.1.6 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.1.7 Artikel 2

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4

- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

6.1.8 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme

- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

6.1.9 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.1.10 Artikel 3

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4

- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

6.1.11 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme

- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

6.2.1 Overview_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see an overview page of different articles. It will give you an orientation of the political classification of each article. Please read the overview carefully. You will be asked a question about it afterwards.

6.2.2 Overview_page

Please click on the link for the overview below and read it carefully. The link will open up in a new window, so return to this question afterwards.

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/O2>

How many political view-points are displayed in the overview?

After reading the article, please answer the question below.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

6.2.3 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.2.4 Artikel 1

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

6.2.5 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

6.2.6 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.2.7 Artikel 2

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

6.2.8 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

6.2.9 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.2.10 Artikel 3

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

6.2.11 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

6.3.1 Overview_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see an overview page of different articles. It will give you an orientation of the political classification of each article. Please read the overview carefully. You will be asked a question about it afterwards.

6.3.2 Overview_page

Please click on the link for the overview below and read it carefully. The link will open up in a new window, so return to this question afterwards.

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/O3>

How many political view-points are displayed in the overview?

After reading the article, please answer the question below.

- 1
- 2

- 3
- 4

6.3.3 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.3.4 Artikel 1

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree

- 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

6.3.5 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2
- 3

- 4
- Very impartial

6.3.6 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.3.7 Artikel 2

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

6.3.8 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial
- 2

- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

6.3.9 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

6.3.10 Artikel 3

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

6.3.11 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial

- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

7.1 Artikel1_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

7.2 Artikel 1

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C1>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

How many illegal immigrants are believed to might have voted, according to the article?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- 5.7 million
- 200 thousand
- more than 50 million
- less than 1 million

How much do you agree with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with the statement "Trump has made repeated claims about massive voter

fraud and election rigging"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
 - 6
 - 7
 - 8
 - 9
 - Strongly agree
-

7.3 Re_occurring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Very fair
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Least extreme
- 2
- 3
- 4
- Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

- Not at all impartial

- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

7.4 Artikel2_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

7.5 Artikel 2

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C2>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

In this article, Senator Marco Rubio has tried to challenge President Trump in the following point:

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- The president's healthcare bill is inefficient.
- Building a wall towards Mexico is a waste of government money.
- Muslims fleeing their persecution in other countries need to be welcomed as allies in the war on extremism.
- The Brexit was an uneuropean move towards more secluded countries.

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting and banning legal permanent residents and refugees from war-torn areas is illegal, immoral and un-American"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "President Trump's executive order targeting

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

Strongly disagree

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

Strongly agree

7.6 Re_occuring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

Very fair

2

3

4

Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

Least extreme

2

3

4

Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

Not at all impartial

- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

7.7 Artikel3_Ankündigung

In the following, you will see a news article on a separate page. Please read it and the contained information carefully. You will be asked questions about it afterwards.

7.8 Artikel 3

If you need to read the article again, click the following link:

<http://winproject.citizendata.de/C3>

Please enter the code at the end of the article in the answer box below.

According to the article, what was the main purpose of the "Fake Universities"?

Please choose the appropriate answer below.

- For communities to steal the tuition money
- To boost voters acceptance for education but don't spend money
- To set up a fake establishment while actually engaging in drug trafficking
- To allow international students to acquire fake Visas

How much do you agree with (believe) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative and it's not entrapment"

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

- Strongly disagree
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- Strongly agree

How much do you believe the public agrees with (believes) the statement "[Setting up a fake university] is creative

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

Strongly disagree

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

Strongly agree

7.9 Re_occuring_end_questions

Rate the extent to which you thought the journalist who wrote the article was biased. Specifically, rate how "fair-minded" the journalist was on a five-point scale.

Please move the slider to the appropriate answer.

Very fair

2

3

4

Very unfair

How politically extreme do you perceive the news article to be?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

Least extreme

2

3

4

Most extreme

How impartial did you think the news report was in dealing with the issue?

Please move the slider below to the appropriate answer.

Not at all impartial

- 2
- 3
- 4
- Very impartial

8 Endseite

Thank you for participating in our survey. You can now enter the following **unique** code into MTurk.

#c_0007#

If the progress bar on this page remains at 93%, that is ok. Please quit the survey and enter the code in Mturk.
